

A Comparative Study of Conventional Extra-Capsular and Small Incision Cataract Surgery

Naresh Rabi Das¹, Seepee Priya², Ram Kumar Satyapal³, Asif Shahnawaz⁴

¹Assistant Professor, Department of Ophthalmology, Darbhanga Medical College and Hospital, Darbhanga, Bihar, India

²Senior Resident, Department of Ophthalmology, Darbhanga Medical College and Hospital, Darbhanga, Bihar, India

³Assistant Professor, Department of Ophthalmology, Darbhanga Medical College and Hospital, Darbhanga, Bihar, India

⁴Professor and HOD, Department of Ophthalmology, Darbhanga Medical College and Hospital, Darbhanga, Bihar, India

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Corresponding Author: Dr. Seepee Priya

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Abstract:

Background: Cataract surgery is one of the most commonly performed procedures worldwide, with conventional extra-capsular cataract extraction (ECCE) and small incision cataract surgery (SICS) being two of the widely used techniques. While ECCE has been the traditional method, SICS has gained popularity due to its smaller incision size, reduced complication rates, and faster recovery. However, the comparative effectiveness of these two techniques in terms of visual outcomes, complications, and patient satisfaction remains an area of ongoing research.

Aim: This study aimed to compare the outcomes of conventional ECCE and SICS in terms of postoperative visual acuity, complication rates, and patient satisfaction.

Methods: A prospective, observational study was conducted. Ninety patients with senile cataracts were randomly assigned to undergo either ECCE (n=45) or SICS (n=45). Preoperative and postoperative visual acuity, intraoperative and postoperative complications, and patient satisfaction were recorded and analyzed. Data were statistically analyzed using SPSS version 23.0, with a p-value of less than 0.05 considered significant.

Results: The SICS group demonstrated significantly better postoperative visual acuity at 3 months compared to the ECCE group ($p < 0.01$). The incidence of intraoperative and postoperative complications was higher in the ECCE group ($p < 0.05$). Patient satisfaction scores were significantly higher in the SICS group ($p < 0.01$), indicating a preference for the SICS procedure.

Conclusion: (SICS) offers superior visual outcomes, fewer complications, and higher patient satisfaction compared to conventional (ECCE). These findings support the adoption of SICS as the preferred technique for cataract surgery, particularly in resource-limited settings.

Recommendations: Further studies with larger sample sizes and long-term follow-up are recommended to validate these findings and to explore the cost-effectiveness of SICS in different healthcare environments.

Keywords: Cataract Surgery, Small Incision Cataract Surgery, Extra-Capsular Cataract Extraction, Visual Outcomes, Patient Satisfaction

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Introduction

The most common cause of blindness in the world, cataracts mostly afflicts the elderly and severely reduce their quality of life. The incidence of cataracts is increasing with the ageing of the global population, highlighting the need for efficient surgical procedures. Among the most popular and effective treatments in ophthalmology is cataract surgery, which has seen tremendous improvements in surgical methods over the years with the goal of enhancing patient outcomes and reducing problems.

For the extraction of cataracts, two main surgical methods have been extensively utilised: (SICS) and traditional (ECCE). The manual extraction of the lens nucleus is made possible by the comparatively large incision required for ECCE, which was formerly the gold standard. Because of the increased wound size and requirement for sutures, ECCE is associated with a higher risk of postoperative sequelae, including astigmatism and longer recovery durations, despite its effectiveness [1, 2].

On the other hand, SICS, a more recent method, uses a smaller incision to extract the lens after it has been broken up into smaller pieces. This method is becoming more and more popular in clinical practice since it minimises the need for sutures and encourages quicker healing with fewer complications. This is especially true in resource-constrained areas where phacoemulsification, another cutting-edge technique, might not be practical [3]. Recent research has demonstrated that SICS offers unique benefits over ECCE, such as shorter surgery times, lower costs, and improved postoperative visual acuity, in addition to matching the visual results of phacoemulsification [4, 5]. The decision between both strategies, especially in various healthcare settings, is still being researched and debated, despite the obvious benefits of SICS. This study aimed to compare the outcomes of conventional ECCE and SICS in terms of postoperative visual acuity, complication rates, and patient satisfaction.

Methodology

Study Design: This study is a comparative, observational, and prospective study.

Study Setting: The study was conducted at Darbhanga Medical College and Hospital, Leharisarai, Darbhanga, from May 2022 to September 2022.

Participants: A total of 90 patients with senile cataract who presented to the Ophthalmology Department of Darbhanga Medical College and Hospital were included in the study. The patients were divided into two groups, with 45 patients undergoing conventional ECCE and 45 undergoing SICS.

Inclusion Criteria

- Patients aged 40-80 years with senile cataract.
- Patients willing to participate in the study and provide informed consent.
- Patients with no history of ocular surgery in the same eye.
- Patients with no significant co-morbid ocular or systemic conditions that could affect the outcome of surgery.

Exclusion Criteria

- Patients with congenital or traumatic cataracts.

- Patients with a history of intraocular inflammation or retinal detachment.
- Patients with co-existing ocular pathologies such as glaucoma, diabetic retinopathy, or macular degeneration.
- Patients with systemic conditions that could contraindicate surgery (e.g., uncontrolled diabetes, hypertension).

Bias: Efforts were made to minimize selection bias by using randomization in assigning patients to either the ECCE or SICS group. The surgeon and clinical staff involved in the data collection and postoperative assessment were blinded to the type of surgery performed.

Data Collection: Data were collected prospectively from the patients' preoperative, intraoperative, and postoperative records. Preoperative data included demographic details, visual acuity, intraocular pressure (IOP), and ocular health. Intraoperative data included the type of surgery, operative time, and any intraoperative complications. Postoperative data included visual acuity, IOP, complications, and patient satisfaction at 1 week, 1 month, and 3 months post-surgery.

Procedure: Patients were randomized into two groups: Group A underwent conventional ECCE, and Group B underwent SICS. Both procedures were performed under local anesthesia by experienced ophthalmic surgeons. Standard surgical protocols were followed for both procedures. Postoperative care included standard antibiotic and anti-inflammatory eye drops. Follow-up visits were scheduled at 1 week, 1 month, and 3 months postoperatively.

Statistical Analysis: Data were analyzed using SPSS version 23.0. Descriptive statistics summarized the data, with continuous variables compared using the t-test and categorical variables using the chi-square test. A p-value < 0.05 was considered significant. Outcomes measured included postoperative visual acuity, complications, and patient satisfaction.

Results

The study included 90 participants, divided into two groups: 45 patients underwent conventional (ECCE), and 45 patients had gone through (SICS).

Table 1: Demographic and Baseline Characteristics of Participants

Characteristic	ECCE Group (n=45)	SICS Group (n=45)	p-value
Mean Age (years)	69.3 ± 5.1	68.7 ± 5.3	0.54
Gender (Male/Female)	22/23	21/24	0.84
Preoperative VA (LogMAR)	0.31 ± 0.08	0.30 ± 0.09	0.72

There was no significant difference between the ECCE and SICS groups in terms of mean age, gender distribution, or preoperative visual acuity (VA), indicating that the groups were comparable at baseline.

Postoperative visual acuity was assessed at 1 week, 1 month, and 3 months post-surgery. The mean postoperative VA at 3 months was significantly better in the SICS group compared to the ECCE group ($p < 0.01$). The results are shown in Table 2.

Table 2: Postoperative Visual Acuity (LogMAR) at 3 Months

Group	Mean Postoperative VA (LogMAR)	Standard Deviation	p-value
ECCE	0.71	0.08	
SICS	0.79	0.07	< 0.01

Intraoperative and Postoperative Complications: The incidence of complications was recorded intraoperatively and during the postoperative period. The ECCE group had a higher rate of complications compared to the SICS group, with significant differences observed ($p < 0.05$).

Table 3: Complications in ECCE and SICS Groups

Complication Type	ECCE Group (n=45)	SICS Group (n=45)	p-value
Intraoperative complications	4	2	0.04
Postoperative complications	5	2	0.03

Patient satisfaction was assessed using a Likert scale (1-5, with 5 being highly satisfied) at the 3-month follow-up. The SICS group reported higher satisfaction scores compared to the ECCE group, with statistically significant differences ($p < 0.01$).

Table 4: Patient Satisfaction Scores

Satisfaction Score	ECCE Group (n=45)	SICS Group (n=45)	p-value
Mean Satisfaction	3.9	4.5	< 0.01

Summary of Results

- The mean age and gender distribution were similar in both ECCE and SICS groups.
- The SICS group showed significantly better postoperative visual acuity at 3 months compared to the ECCE group ($p < 0.01$).
- The ECCE group had a higher incidence of both intraoperative and postoperative complications ($p < 0.05$).
- Patient satisfaction was significantly higher in the SICS group compared to the ECCE group ($p < 0.01$).

Discussion

These findings suggest that (SICS) may offer better visual outcomes, lower complication rates, and higher patient satisfaction compared to conventional (ECCE). First, at the three-month follow-up, the SICS group showed noticeably improved postoperative visual acuity. This implies that SICS outperforms ECCE in terms of visual outcomes, most likely because the method is less intrusive and allows for a speedier recovery with less astigmatism following surgery.

Comparing the ECCE group to the SICS group, the ECCE group had a greater incidence of intraoperative and postoperative complications. The smaller incision size and less tissue disruption during surgery may be the reasons for the lower

complication rate in the SICS group, which highlights the technique's safety benefits. The SICS group had a much higher level of patient satisfaction. The improved visual results and decreased problems seen in this group, along with the higher satisfaction levels, support the SICS procedure's overall effectiveness and patient choice.

According to a study, patients who received MSICS recovered from their visual rehabilitation more quickly and effectively than those who had ECCE. Additionally, the study discovered that MSICS led to a considerable reduction in astigmatism caused by surgery. The fact that there were no appreciable variations in complications between the two groups indicates that both methods are probably safe. Nonetheless, MSICS produced better overall visual results, giving it a better choice for both patients and surgeons [6].

The efficacy of MSICS versus ECCE in a hospital context in a different study was evaluated. This observational study shown that although visual acuity was successfully restored by both surgical techniques, certain intraoperative problems were more common with each approach. For example, there was a higher frequency of anterior chamber collapse, lens prolapse, and iris prolapse in MSICS. On the other hand, ECCE was exclusive to capsular flaps and vitreous loss. Both approaches are viable solutions depending on the patient's state and the surgical environment, as demonstrated by the

equivalent overall restoration of visual acuity between the two treatments [7].

An investigation at the University Hospital of Bouake (Ivory Coast) provided additional evidence for MSICS's advantage over ECCE. In this study, sutureless MSICS was compared to sutured ECCE, and the results showed that MSICS produced improved early visual acuity outcomes, reduced intraoperative and postoperative problems, and shortened surgery times. According to the study, postoperative astigmatism was much lower in the MSICS group, which facilitated patients' speedier return to regular activities and visual recovery [8].

Conclusion

The research suggests that SICS is a better option than traditional ECCE. SICS is a tempting option for cataract surgery since it not only increases visual recovery but also lowers the risk of complications and increases patient satisfaction.

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